

Tutorial Series on Java Framework for Evolutionary Computation and Decision Making

Tutorial 7: Visualization module – Drawing Arrows

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The framework version used when preparing the document: 1.01 (Java v. 17.0; IntelliJ IDEA 2023.3.8).

Abstract

This tutorial showcases an update to the Visualization module that allows rendering arrows. It also introduces a few minor additions.

Keywords: JECDM, visualization, interactive tool, experimental verification

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1. Introduction [T]

Source package: `t1_t10.t7_drawing_arrows`

This tutorial (updated) introduces a few minor updates to the Visualization module:

- Constructing data sets can now be done via *Visualization.dataset.DSFactory2D* and *DSFactory3D* classes. New methods for constructing data sets will be supplied to these two classes in the future, ignoring the *DataSet* class.
- The interpretation of line contiguity can be altered now. Previously, the breaks could only be introduced by adding a null to the general *LinkedList<double[][]>* data input. Now, one can specify that each subsequent pair of entries in *double[][]* constitutes a single line. This change can be achieved by adjusting the “*treatContiguousLinesAsBroken*” flag, which can be passed via the *DataSet* constructors in *DSFactory2D* and *DSFactory3D*.
- When drawing a gradient line, a dedicated painter decomposes two points that are supposed to represent a line with a series of intermediate points (linearly interpolated, equally spaced). This way, accurate coloring may be executed, even if the two original points are distant. The number of these points depends on the distance between the inspected points and a threshold-like parameter that dictates

the maximum allowed distance for not decomposing the line. This parameter can now be adjusted via the *DataSet* constructors in *DSFactory2D* and *DSFactory3D* (see the “*gradientLineMinSegmentLength*” parameter).

- This update allows drawing arrows using the data sets (in 2D and 3D mode). For this purpose, another style class: *ArrowStyles* is introduced. It dictates the overall shape of the arrow, i.e., whether the arrow should be placed at the beginning and/or at the end of a contiguous line, arrow width/length, style (currently only two styles are available), and color (mono or gradient). Data sets renderable as arrows can be obtained via constructors in *DSFactory2D* and *DSFactory3D*. Important note: arrows (their heads) are rendered only when the line style is specified.
- The plot legend is slightly altered now (thus, differences with the previous version may be observable). Additionally, one can now specify the limit for the number of entries in one legend column. Multiple, equally spaced columns will be produced if the limit is exceeded.

Useful tutorial source codes are provided in the specific source package. Since they are straightforward and commented, they are not discussed here. Figures 1-6 illustrate their expected outputs for convenience.

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Figure 1: Expected visualization for *Tutorial1a*

Figure 3: Expected visualization for *Tutorial2a*

Figure 2: Expected visualization for *Tutorial1b*

Figure 4: Expected visualization for *Tutorial2b*

Figure 5: Expected visualization for *Tutorial2c*

Figure 6: Expected visualization for *Tutorial2d*